

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory
4901 Hawkins NE
Albuquerque, NM 87109
TEL: 505-345-3975 FAX: 505-345-4107
Website: www.hallenvironmental.com

May 01, 2020

Michael Jones

National Cave and Karst Research Institute
400-1 Cascades Ave
Carlsbad, NM 88220
TEL: (830) 312-8131
FAX

RE: San Solomon Spring

OrderNo.: 2004957

Dear Michael Jones:

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory received 1 sample(s) on 4/22/2020 for the analyses presented in the following report.

These were analyzed according to EPA procedures or equivalent. To access our accredited tests please go to www.hallenvironmental.com or the state specific web sites. In order to properly interpret your results, it is imperative that you review this report in its entirety. See the sample checklist and/or the Chain of Custody for information regarding the sample receipt temperature and preservation. Data qualifiers or a narrative will be provided if the sample analysis or analytical quality control parameters require a flag. When necessary, data qualifiers are provided on both the sample analysis report and the QC summary report, both sections should be reviewed. All samples are reported, as received, unless otherwise indicated. Lab measurement of analytes considered field parameters that require analysis within 15 minutes of sampling such as pH and residual chlorine are qualified as being analyzed outside of the recommended holding time.

Please don't hesitate to contact HEAL for any additional information or clarifications.

ADHS Cert #AZ0682 -- NMED-DWB Cert #NM9425 -- NMED-Micro Cert #NM0901

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Andy Freeman', is written in a cursive style.

Andy Freeman
Laboratory Manager
4901 Hawkins NE
Albuquerque, NM 87109

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

Analytical Report

Lab Order 2004957

Date Reported: 5/1/2020

CLIENT: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Client Sample ID: San Solomon Spring

Project: San Solomon Spring

Collection Date: 4/20/2020 12:00:00 PM

Lab ID: 2004957-001

Matrix: AQUEOUS

Received Date: 4/22/2020 9:20:00 AM

Analyses	Result	RL	Qual	Units	DF	Date Analyzed
EPA METHOD 8015M/D: DIESEL RANGE						Analyst: BRM
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	ND	1.0		mg/L	1	4/27/2020 2:36:48 PM
Motor Oil Range Organics (MRO)	ND	5.0		mg/L	1	4/27/2020 2:36:48 PM
Surr: DNOP	114	70-130		%Rec	1	4/27/2020 2:36:48 PM
EPA METHOD 8270C: PAHS						Analyst: DAM
Naphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
1-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
2-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Acenaphthylene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Acenaphthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Fluorene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Phenanthrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Benz(a)anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Chrysene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Benzo(a)pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ND	0.50		µg/L	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Surr: N-hexadecane	80.1	48.1-106		%Rec	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	106	43.3-97.7	S	%Rec	1	4/29/2020 8:40:59 PM
EPA METHOD 8260: VOLATILES SHORT LIST						Analyst: DJF
Benzene	ND	1.0		µg/L	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Toluene	ND	1.0		µg/L	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Ethylbenzene	ND	1.0		µg/L	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Xylenes, Total	ND	1.5		µg/L	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Surr: 1,2-Dichloroethane-d4	90.5	70-130		%Rec	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Surr: Dibromofluoromethane	99.7	70-130		%Rec	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Surr: Toluene-d8	101	70-130		%Rec	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
EPA METHOD 8015D: GASOLINE RANGE						Analyst: DJF
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	ND	0.050		mg/L	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM
Surr: BFB	100	70-130		%Rec	1	4/25/2020 12:51:46 AM

Refer to the QC Summary report and sample login checklist for flagged QC data and preservation information.

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
E Value above quantitation range
J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
P Sample pH Not In Range
RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2004957

01-May-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Project: San Solomon Spring

Sample ID: LCS-52065	SampType: LCS	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: 52065	RunNo: 68435								
Prep Date: 4/24/2020	Analysis Date: 4/27/2020	SeqNo: 2368094	Units: mg/L							
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	5.4	1.0	5.000	0	108	70	130			
Surr: DNOP	0.55		0.5000		110	70	130			

Sample ID: MB-52065	SampType: MBLK	TestCode: EPA Method 8015M/D: Diesel Range								
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: 52065	RunNo: 68435								
Prep Date: 4/24/2020	Analysis Date: 4/27/2020	SeqNo: 2368095	Units: mg/L							
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Diesel Range Organics (DRO)	ND	1.0								
Motor Oil Range Organics (MRO)	ND	5.0								
Surr: DNOP	1.1		1.000		111	70	130			

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
E Value above quantitation range
J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
P Sample pH Not In Range
RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2004957

01-May-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute
Project: San Solomon Spring

Sample ID: mb1	SampType: MBLK		TestCode: EPA Method 8260: Volatiles Short List							
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: SL68408		RunNo: 68408							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 4/24/2020		SeqNo: 2366720		Units: µg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Benzene	ND	1.0								
Toluene	ND	1.0								
Ethylbenzene	ND	1.0								
Xylenes, Total	ND	1.5								
Surr: 1,2-Dichloroethane-d4	9.2		10.00		91.9	70	130			
Surr: 4-Bromofluorobenzene	10		10.00		101	70	130			
Surr: Dibromofluoromethane	9.7		10.00		97.0	70	130			
Surr: Toluene-d8	10		10.00		99.6	70	130			

Sample ID: 100ng lcs	SampType: LCS		TestCode: EPA Method 8260: Volatiles Short List							
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: SL68408		RunNo: 68408							
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 4/24/2020		SeqNo: 2366721		Units: µg/L					
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Benzene	20	1.0	20.00	0	98.6	70	130			
Toluene	21	1.0	20.00	0	106	70	130			
Surr: 1,2-Dichloroethane-d4	9.3		10.00		93.0	70	130			
Surr: 4-Bromofluorobenzene	10		10.00		101	70	130			
Surr: Dibromofluoromethane	9.5		10.00		95.3	70	130			
Surr: Toluene-d8	9.5		10.00		95.0	70	130			

Qualifiers:

- | | |
|---|---|
| * Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level. | B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank |
| D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix | E Value above quantitation range |
| H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded | J Analyte detected below quantitation limits |
| ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit | P Sample pH Not In Range |
| PQL Practical Quantitative Limit | RL Reporting Limit |
| S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix | |

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2004957

01-May-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute
Project: San Solomon Spring

Sample ID: ics-52102		SampType: LCS			TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs					
Client ID: LCSW		Batch ID: 52102			RunNo: 68528					
Prep Date: 4/27/2020		Analysis Date: 4/29/2020			SeqNo: 2371596		Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Naphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	71.1	41.8	97.8			
1-Methylnaphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	70.6	44.7	104			
2-Methylnaphthalene	13	0.50	20.00	0	64.1	45	101			
Acenaphthylene	16	0.50	20.00	0	81.8	51.2	102			
Acenaphthene	16	0.50	20.00	0	80.8	53.2	101			
Fluorene	15	0.50	20.00	0	77.2	57.6	106			
Phenanthrene	16	0.50	20.00	0	79.6	57.6	109			
Anthracene	16	0.50	20.00	0	82.3	56.1	98.9			
Fluoranthene	18	0.50	20.00	0	87.8	61.4	114			
Pyrene	130	0.50	20.00	0	626	58	110			ES
Benz(a)anthracene	140	0.50	20.00	0	686	60	102			ES
Chrysene	140	0.50	20.00	0	718	50.8	93.4			ES
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	19	0.50	20.00	0	95.0	56.2	118			
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	19	0.50	20.00	0	96.8	57.7	119			
Benzo(a)pyrene	20	0.50	20.00	0	101	55.5	114			
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	25	0.50	20.00	0	127	53	110			S
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	22	0.50	20.00	0	108	55	113			
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	20	0.50	20.00	0	101	51.2	115			
Surr: N-hexadecane	71		87.60		81.4	48.1	106			
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	22		20.00		111	43.3	97.7			S

Sample ID: icsd-52102		SampType: LCSD			TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs					
Client ID: LCSS02		Batch ID: 52102			RunNo: 68528					
Prep Date: 4/27/2020		Analysis Date: 4/29/2020			SeqNo: 2371597		Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Naphthalene	16	0.50	20.00	0	78.0	41.8	97.8	9.26	25.4	
1-Methylnaphthalene	16	0.50	20.00	0	81.8	44.7	104	14.7	21.5	
2-Methylnaphthalene	14	0.50	20.00	0	72.5	45	101	12.3	25.2	
Acenaphthylene	17	0.50	20.00	0	85.4	51.2	102	4.31	30.3	
Acenaphthene	18	0.50	20.00	0	90.0	53.2	101	10.8	28.1	
Fluorene	17	0.50	20.00	0	87.1	57.6	106	12.1	33	
Phenanthrene	15	0.50	20.00	0	77.2	57.6	109	3.06	24.5	
Anthracene	16	0.50	20.00	0	79.1	56.1	98.9	3.97	26.9	
Fluoranthene	16	0.50	20.00	0	79.1	61.4	114	10.4	21.8	
Pyrene	120	0.50	20.00	0	601	58	110	4.08	27	ES
Benz(a)anthracene	130	0.50	20.00	0	662	60	102	3.59	27.4	ES
Chrysene	140	0.50	20.00	0	680	50.8	93.4	5.41	20.4	ES
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	19	0.50	20.00	0	95.5	56.2	118	0.525	22.5	

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
E Value above quantitation range
J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
P Sample pH Not In Range
RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2004957

01-May-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute
Project: San Solomon Spring

Sample ID: lcsd-52102		SampType: LCSD		TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs						
Client ID: LCSS02		Batch ID: 52102		RunNo: 68528						
Prep Date: 4/27/2020		Analysis Date: 4/29/2020		SeqNo: 2371597			Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	20	0.50	20.00	0	99.0	57.7	119	2.25	24.1	
Benzo(a)pyrene	19	0.50	20.00	0	96.2	55.5	114	4.87	27.3	
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	26	0.50	20.00	0	129	53	110	1.64	18.5	S
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	21	0.50	20.00	0	103	55	113	5.41	28.4	
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	20	0.50	20.00	0	98.4	51.2	115	2.61	21.8	
Surr: N-hexadecane	77		87.60		87.9	48.1	106	0	0	
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	21		20.00		105	43.3	97.7	0	0	S

Sample ID: mb-52102		SampType: MBLK		TestCode: EPA Method 8270C: PAHs						
Client ID: PBW		Batch ID: 52102		RunNo: 68528						
Prep Date: 4/27/2020		Analysis Date: 4/29/2020		SeqNo: 2371598			Units: µg/L			
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Naphthalene	ND	0.50								
1-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50								
2-Methylnaphthalene	ND	0.50								
Acenaphthylene	ND	0.50								
Acenaphthene	ND	0.50								
Fluorene	ND	0.50								
Phenanthrene	ND	0.50								
Anthracene	ND	0.50								
Fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Pyrene	ND	0.50								
Benz(a)anthracene	ND	0.50								
Chrysene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(a)pyrene	ND	0.50								
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	ND	0.50								
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ND	0.50								
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ND	0.50								
Surr: N-hexadecane	59		87.60		67.7	48.1	106			
Surr: Benzo(e)pyrene	16		20.00		79.6	43.3	97.7			

Qualifiers:

- * Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
- D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
- H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
- ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
- PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
- S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix
- B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
- E Value above quantitation range
- J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
- P Sample pH Not In Range
- RL Reporting Limit

QC SUMMARY REPORT

Hall Environmental Analysis Laboratory, Inc.

WO#: 2004957

01-May-20

Client: National Cave and Karst Research Institute

Project: San Solomon Spring

Sample ID: mb1	SampType: MBLK	TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range								
Client ID: PBW	Batch ID: GW68408	RunNo: 68408								
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 4/24/2020	SeqNo: 2366742	Units: mg/L							
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	ND	0.050								
Surr: BFB	9.9		10.00		98.9	70	130			

Sample ID: 2.5ug gro lcs	SampType: LCS	TestCode: EPA Method 8015D: Gasoline Range								
Client ID: LCSW	Batch ID: GW68408	RunNo: 68408								
Prep Date:	Analysis Date: 4/24/2020	SeqNo: 2366743	Units: mg/L							
Analyte	Result	PQL	SPK value	SPK Ref Val	%REC	LowLimit	HighLimit	%RPD	RPDLimit	Qual
Gasoline Range Organics (GRO)	0.51	0.050	0.5000	0	101	70	130			
Surr: BFB	10		10.00		101	70	130			

Qualifiers:

* Value exceeds Maximum Contaminant Level.
D Sample Diluted Due to Matrix
H Holding times for preparation or analysis exceeded
ND Not Detected at the Reporting Limit
PQL Practical Quantitative Limit
S % Recovery outside of range due to dilution or matrix

B Analyte detected in the associated Method Blank
E Value above quantitation range
J Analyte detected below quantitation limits
P Sample pH Not In Range
RL Reporting Limit

Sample Log-In Check List

Client Name: **NATIONAL CAVE AND K** Work Order Number: **2004957** RcptNo: 1

Received By: **Isaiah Ortiz** **4/22/2020 9:20:00 AM** *I-Ox*
 Completed By: **Isaiah Ortiz** **4/22/2020 10:30:32 AM** *I-Ox*
 Reviewed By: *LB* *4/22/20*

Chain of Custody

1. Is Chain of Custody sufficiently complete? Yes No Not Present
 2. How was the sample delivered? UPS

Log In

3. Was an attempt made to cool the samples? Yes No NA
 4. Were all samples received at a temperature of >0° C to 6.0°C Yes No NA
 5. Sample(s) in proper container(s)? Yes No
 6. Sufficient sample volume for indicated test(s)? Yes No
 7. Are samples (except VOA and ONG) properly preserved? Yes No
 8. Was preservative added to bottles? Yes No NA
 9. Received at least 1 vial with headspace <1/4" for AQ VOA? Yes No NA
 10. Were any sample containers received broken? Yes No
 11. Does paperwork match bottle labels? Yes No
 (Note discrepancies on chain of custody)
 12. Are matrices correctly identified on Chain of Custody? Yes No
 13. Is it clear what analyses were requested? Yes No
 14. Were all holding times able to be met? Yes No
 (If no, notify customer for authorization.)

of preserved bottles checked for pH: _____
 (<2 or >12 unless noted)
 Adjusted? _____
 Checked by: *JR 4/22/20*

Special Handling (if applicable)

15. Was client notified of all discrepancies with this order? Yes No NA

Person Notified:	_____	Date:	_____
By Whom:	_____	Via:	<input type="checkbox"/> eMail <input type="checkbox"/> Phone <input type="checkbox"/> Fax <input type="checkbox"/> In Person
Regarding:	_____		
Client Instructions:	_____		

16. Additional remarks:

Cooler Information

Cooler No	Temp °C	Condition	Seal Intact	Seal No	Seal Date	Signed By
1	3.6	Good	Not Present			

